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APPLICATION OF FUZZY MODELING FOR TASK ALLOCATION IN IT PROJECT MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Distribution and allocation of resources belong to complex multicriteria tasks. In relation to this, in the management of projects involving the creation of informational products, there is a pressing need to develop efficient and versatile methods for optimal task allocation among performers. One possible tool to enhance the justification of decisions made by the project manager of companies engaged in the development of informational products can be fuzzy logic, allowing for the handling of poorly structured and imprecise information using natural language.

The article proposes a fuzzy model for managing IT project tasks, enabling the use of natural language categories with the aim of enhancing decision-making efficiency under uncertain conditions and reducing costs in the event of adverse situations. The characteristics of a project to create an informational product are discussed, a standard scheme of the task management process in an IT project is developed, and the appropriateness of using the apparatus of fuzzy systems for task management is demonstrated. Using the mathematical apparatus of fuzzy logic will allow the project manager to work with variables expressed in qualitative categories, without resorting to average values, thus enhancing the quality of decisions made in project management.

Within the scope of the work, the task of evaluating the success of task execution by developers is considered. Six input linguistic variables and one output have been identified, for each of which term sets and membership functions have been developed. An expert rule base has been constructed, comprising 81 production rules; a fuzzy system model for task management based on the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox for MatLab has been developed. The Mamdani algorithm is employed as the fuzzy inference scheme. The results of the model's functioning are presented, which may prove useful for IT project managers in practice.

Keywords: IT project, management of the project for the creation of an informational product, task management, fuzzy systems, linguistic variables, membership functions, Fuzzy Logic Toolbox for MatLab.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

One of the means to achieve effective results, aiding in success and profitability across various economic sectors, is increasingly becoming project management. This methodology is most often employed by outsourcing firms when executing IT projects. Managing a project focused on the development of information products is a massive, resource-intensive, and intricate endeavor that demands high competency from the involved experts. The main distinction between an IT project and projects in other sectors (like construction, manufacturing, etc.) lies in the fact that project management in the realm of informatization interacts with intangible outcomes.

Decision-making in the context of IT projects often takes place under conditions of insufficient information and ambiguous specifications, complicating the achievement of a high-quality information product. Additionally, project managers should consider the human factor, as the quality of the information product, its cost, and even the profit of the IT company depend on the experience and knowledge of developers. This makes the task of duty and resource allocation one of the most pivotal in a project manager's work.

This challenge belongs to the class of multicriteria tasks, where criteria aren't always quantitatively expressed. Hence, employing traditional mathematical methods might be ineffective. Enhancing the efficiency

of task assignments to developers can be achieved using tools grounded on fuzzy systems methods. In this regard, in IT project management, it's pertinent to devise methods for the optimal distribution of tasks among participants.

ANALYSIS OF RECENT STUDIES AND PUBLICATIONS

Effective allocation and planning of tasks are key factors for the successful implementation of complex IT projects. Optimal utilization of available resources and rational planning of work allow for adherence to deadlines, budget, and quality requirements of the project. However, the task of allocating tasks and resources is extremely challenging due to the high dynamics and uncertainty in the conditions of IT project implementation.

In recent years, significant attention has been given to the application of fuzzy modeling methods to address planning and resource allocation tasks in IT project management. Fuzzy models allow for accounting inaccuracies in the initial data, probabilistic factors, and qualitative characteristics, which are crucial when modeling the behavior and interactions of human resources.

In the article by G. Antucheviciene et al. [2], a fuzzy stochastic optimization model is proposed to solve the problem of staff allocation in IT projects. This model takes into account uncertainties and probabilistic factors related to resource availability, productivity of

employees, etc. Experimental research confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

S. Chatterjee and S. Dey [3] explored the use of fuzzy hierarchy analysis for task distribution in software projects based on risk assessment. This approach allows for consideration of qualitative factors when determining the priorities for task distribution among team members.

H. Son et al. [4] proposed a fuzzy logic model for assigning tasks to multi-skilled team members in software development, allowing flexible task distribution taking into account the competencies of participants.

Research by X. Wang et al. [5] focuses on an optimization model based on fuzzy logic for collaborative product development, enabling effective task allocation under uncertain initial data conditions.

In the work of S.-J. Chen and J. Lin [6], the application of fuzzy set theory for modeling participant characteristics when forming multi-skilled teams in engineering projects is proposed. This approach allows for inaccuracies in evaluating the competencies of team members.

Research by A. Barreto et al. [7] addresses the resource allocation problem in IT projects using fuzzy multi-criteria optimization. Such an optimization model allows for both quantitative and qualitative factors to be taken into account when distributing resources.

The article by P. Saurav et al. [8] proposes a hybrid approach, combining particle swarm optimization with fuzzy logic for project planning with limited resources. This approach ensures effective search for optimal resource allocation.

K. Goyal et al. [9] explore the application of fuzzy K-means clustering and genetic algorithms for forming teams in IT projects based on participants' skills, optimizing team composition.

The discussed approaches to constructing fuzzy optimization models, methodologies for combining fuzzy logic with heuristic and evolutionary algorithms, have been reviewed. The analysis confirms the effectiveness and prospects of applying fuzzy modeling in IT project management, but the specific issue of applying fuzzy modeling to task allocation in IT project management requires more thorough analysis and research.

OBJECTIVES OF THE ARTICLE

The aim of this article is to develop a fuzzy model for task allocation in IT project management under conditions of uncertainty, which allows for optimal utilization of human resources considering their competencies and workload, to enhance the efficiency of management decision-making.

THE MAIN MATERIAL OF THE RESEARCH

In managing IT projects, there are key distinctions defined by the specifics of the information product creation process [1, 10]:

- the information product, as the final stage of the IT project, is intangible and cannot be measured in universally recognized units. Therefore, the preparation of tasks and work related to the IT project must be extremely accurate. Each IT project is unique, and unlike projects in

construction or manufacturing, such projects don't have standard costs for typical actions. The project deadlines can only be estimated roughly based on the experience of implementing similar tasks in comparable projects;

- throughout the project lifecycle, requirements for the final information product frequently change, leading to a complex process of modification and requirement alignment;

- as a result of the previous point, most development processes are uncontrollable. This is because the client's vision of the end result is often rather general, and the process of creating a quality information product is hard to formalize. Thus, precise planning of the necessary work and tasks is nearly impossible;

- the efficiency of IT projects directly depends on the qualifications of the participants. There is often a lack of highly skilled professionals in the market;

- there is a wide variety of tools and platforms for development. The more modern and powerful the tool used, the fewer specialists who master it;

- there are many different models and methodologies for developing information products: standards, SW-CMM, Rational Unified Process, Microsoft Solutions Framework, Extreme Programming, Scrum, and others. Each has its pros and cons. Companies often have to adapt the best methods to fit their needs. Any attempts to implement solely one development methodology for information products proves futile, as the development process itself is unpredictable and non-formalized.

IT project managers must take into account the aspects that determine project complexity and respond to them using specific management techniques for such projects. The final list of these aspects, their significance, and criticality vary depending on the specific project.

In addition to characteristics directly related to project implementation, it is important to consider characteristics of the IT industry itself, which indirectly influence the success of IT projects.

Firstly, there is a high turnover rate of staff in the IT sector. To prevent the loss of skills acquired by experienced professionals and reduce the adaptation time of a newcomer to a project, it's essential to develop a knowledge management system.

Secondly, there's a lack of mechanisms to motivate work. While the IT industry offers relatively high salaries, there is a shortage of professionals. This results in a high staff turnover rate; it's easier to lure a specialist from a competitor than to upskill existing employees.

Thirdly, there are several external factors negatively impacting IT companies: a high level of cyber threats, imperfect legislation, and the absence of an effective system for training future IT professionals.

According to the PMBoK, a crucial aspect in the knowledge area is managing a company's human resources, specifically the effective management of the project team. Concerning the degree of participation in the development process of an information product, project participants can be classified into three categories: core team, auxiliary team, and stakeholders. The developed role model for information product development is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Role Model for Information Product Development.	
Role	Area of Responsibility
Project Manager	Team formation Creation of a communication environment Development of plans, including: – Estimation of task duration and labor intensity during planning; – Task distribution within the team Overseeing plan execution, which includes: – Monitoring plan progress; – Ensuring team activities align with the business process of development; – Organizational tasks (including interactions with the client); – Part of the analytical work
Analyst	Collecting client requirements Development of the project's technical specifications Refinement of specifications Creating test plans Conceptual testing of functionality Development of user documentation
Technical Leader	Development of the conceptual architecture of the solution Development of the working project design Quality control of code and ensuring its adherence to architectural designs Participation in planning and estimating task complexity and duration Participation in comprehensive testing
Developers	Developing functionality Code quality checks Debugging and error corrections Initial code testing Participation in comprehensive code testing
Tester	Functionality testing Writing unit-tests Participation in developing test plans

In the context of project management, a significant part of a project manager's work involves assigning tasks to the team as a whole and to each member individually, as well as subsequent monitoring of their execution. The structural model of the IT project task management business process is illustrated in Figure 1.

One of the common tools for defining roles and responsibilities among team members is the creation of the RACI matrix (Responsible, Accountable, Consult before

doing, Inform after doing). The result is a table that describes the involvement of different roles in task execution. Unfortunately, there are no clear guidelines on what a project manager should base their decision on when assigning tasks to a specific executor.

A task management system is a set of tools for formulating tasks and monitoring their execution, offering a range of functional capabilities: creating a new task, assigning responsibilities, setting access rights, and defining the scope of work for the task.

Fig. 1 – Structural model of the business process of task management in an IT project.

The operating procedure of the task management system is standard and includes the following stages:

- task formulation, i.e., defining its content, author, executor, and controller;
- determining the task completion deadline: the author can set a fixed deadline or give this option to the executor;
- task execution: the executor indicates the completion;
- performance check: the controller-tester analyzes the quality of the task's completion, after which the task can be finished or sent back for revisions;
- notifying the author about task completion.

Task management systems for projects are widely available in the market. There's a plethora of both commercial and free software. Some of the most renowned ones include Asana, Basecamp, JIRA, Redmine, Bitrix24, Trello, MS Project, and more. Analysis showed that software for task management primarily focuses on monitoring task execution. However, the question of why a particular task is assigned to a specific expert remains unanswered and is often intuitively decided by the project manager based on his experience.

From a technical standpoint, automating task management seems simple. The main challenge lies in accurately reflecting the management model and style adopted in the organization. Therefore, task management programs must be tailored to a specific approach to human resource management. It's crucial to remember that merely having a task management system doesn't guarantee increased productivity because the core issues of communication and task control persist.

The task distribution process is a complex task with many criteria, involving the allocation of resources by types of work and identifying executors, considering their workload, qualification, and specialization. Traditional methods such as game theory or the assignment problem,

with its subsequent solution using the Hungarian algorithm, often don't apply in managerial practices. Conventional game theory methods in the specific conditions of IT projects are also not suitable since there's no opportunity to gather statistical data for each alternative task solution.

Tasks associated with project management are characterized by the manager's high responsibility, a variable project structure as a system with uncertainty and contradictory information. The project team needs to address undefined and poorly structured problems, for which it's challenging to apply standard methods and models. In such conditions, fuzzy logic becomes a tool to solve these issues.

The foundation for creating fuzzy systems is the fuzzy modeling toolkit, which relies on methods of formalization and analysis of poorly structured and incomplete information arising due to the inherent complexity of objects and processes. The uniqueness of fuzzy systems lies in the use of linguistic variables to describe the modeled system's activity, based either on expert conclusions in a particular field or on prior research of statistical data.

Based on the work of Kosko B. [11], specifically the theorem on fuzzy approximation, it states that any mathematical structure can be approximated using a system based on fuzzy logic. Thus, using "IF..., THEN..." rules and their further formalization through fuzzy logic, one can reproduce any "input-output" relationship without the use of complex differential and integral computations traditionally used in management. Nowadays, fuzzy logic is a well-studied and known tool for solving tasks in the fields of management and decision-making.

Distinct features of fuzzy systems [12, 13] include:

- the ability to work with vague input data, such as values that constantly change over time (dynamic tasks) or values that cannot be precisely defined numerically;

– the possibility to forgo complex management systems based on the solution of differential equations if it matches the required accuracy of calculations;

– describing the decision-making process in an understandable language, using subjective and human-familiar qualitative assessments, and linking these assessments with a clear mathematical system;

– the ability to make qualitative evaluations of input and output data.

Within the scope of task management, there is an issue of assessing the efficiency of tasks performed by developers. Other project participants are not taken into account since in every project, roles such as the project manager, analyst, technical writer, tester, typically have one individual assigned. Therefore, when a specific task arises (writing documentation, analytical task, testing, etc.), it

can only be assigned to an employee with the necessary specialization. Within a project, tasks aimed at developing information products always outnumber the developers. Thus, one of the key problems facing a project manager is the proper assignment of tasks to them.

The following input linguistic variables and their sets were identified:– complexity {low, average, high} – складність {низька, середня, висока};

– laborintensity {low, average, high};

– novelty {new, rare, typical};

– priority {non-critical, urgent, critical};

– developer {Junior, Middle, Senior};

– employment {low, average, high, very high}.

The membership functions of input variables are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 – Membership functions of input variables: a) task complexity, b) task labor intensity, c) novelty of the task, d) task priority, e) developer's professionalism, f) project involvement.

The output variable used was the variable result {unsatisfactory, satisfactory, successful} which translates to "result" {unsatisfactory, satisfactory, successful} – the efficiency of task execution, the membership functions of which are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 – Membership functions of the output variable.

As a result of expert analysis, 81 most significant rules were formulated. Here are a few examples from them: 1) IF complexity average AND laborintensity low

AND novelty typical AND priority non-critical AND developer Junior AND employment low THEN result successful

- 2) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority non-critical AND developer Middle AND employment average THEN result successful
- 3) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority non-critical AND developer Middle AND employment higt THEN result satisfactory
- 4) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority AND developer Senior AND employment higt THEN result satisfactory
- 5) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND urgent priority AND developer Senior AND employment very high THEN result satisfactory
- 6) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority critical AND developer Middle AND employment average THEN result satisfactory
- 7) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority critical AND developer Middle AND employment higt THEN result unsatisfactory
- 8) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty new AND priority critical AND developer Senior And employment big TO result satisfactory

9) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty rare AND priority non-critical AND developer Middle AND employment low TO result successful

10) IF complexity average AND laborintensity average AND novelty rare AND priority non-critical AND developer Middle And employment high TO result satisfactory

To create the fuzzy inference system, the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox in Matlab was employed. In Matlab, there are five primary graphical interface tools available: editors for fuzzy inference, membership functions, inference rules, and tools for viewing rules and the inference surface. They interact with one another, so changes in one lead to changes in the others [14].

Using the FIS Editor utility, we set the following parameters for the fuzzy inference system: type - Mamdani, methods of aggregation, accumulation, and defuzzification, as well as all the inputs and outputs of the fuzzy system.

Membership functions for variables were established in the corresponding windows. For example, for the variable "Task Complexity," a trapezoidal membership function was chosen with specification for each member. Other variables were defined similarly.

The final step in creating the system was to determine a set of rules that establish the relationship between input variables and outputs (Figure 4).

Fig. 4 – Expert rule base establishing the relationship between input variables and outputs.

The rule visualization tool allows showcasing the fuzzy inference process and obtaining the result (Figure 5).

Fig. 5 – Rule visualization window.

The main window of this tool includes multiple smaller windows, arranged in a matrix format. The number of rows corresponds to the number of rules, and the columns correspond to the number of input and output variables. Each window displays the relevant membership function, its level, and contribution to the overall result [14]. To analyze the efficiency of task execution by developers, values of input variables are entered, and the result is displayed in the opposite corner. The system also offers the possibility to visualize the inference surface depending on two input parameters.

The assessment of the efficiency of executing each individual task is personal. The fuzzy modeling methodology will assist the project manager in identifying the positive and negative aspects of resolving a task when assigned to a specific performer and making necessary adjustments to their decision.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the IT project management process overall, and the task execution process in particular, revealed the presence of uncertainties, poorly structured, and subjective data, hindering the achievement of the desired final result. The proposed fuzzy model for task management is flexible, meaning project managers can incorporate new input parameters specific to a certain IT project. This will only alter the number of rules while preserving the logic of the model.

The practical value of the obtained results lies in the fact that applying the mathematical tools of fuzzy logic will allow the project manager to work with parameters expressed in qualitative categories, without resorting to

average indicators. This, in the end, will reduce the subjectivity of the decisions made.

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